

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Data management plan 1st 2nd

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Data management plan.....	2
1.1	Data summary.....	2
1.2	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) Data.....	4
1.2.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	4
1.2.2	Making data accessible	4
1.2.3	Making data interoperable.....	7
1.2.4	Increase data re-use	8
1.3	Other research outputs	9
1.4	Allocation of resources.....	10
1.5	Data security	11
1.6	Ethics.....	11
1.7	Other issues.....	11

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Data Management Plan

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METROLOGY PARTNERSHIP |

1 Data management plan

1.1 Data summary

Questions	Answers
<p>1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use them for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.</p>	<p>This project re-used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal pre-existing data from the participants • Publicly available data such as peer-reviewed articles found in scientific literature <p>These data were used for the selection and assessment of uncertainty of the instrumentation and methods developed in the project, as input for calculations or for comparison with new measurements carried out in the project, and for validation of the project's results.</p> <p>The datasets were re-used in WP1 for validating the metrology framework of soil moisture measurement, and in WP3 and WP4 for assessing the uncertainty of the CRNS-based soil moisture estimates and for the comparison of the CNRS-based soil moisture values against the point-scale sensors' reading and soil moisture determined from the soil samples.</p> <p>No existing data has been considered for re-use and then discarded.</p>
<p>2 What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?</p>	<p>The actual produced data formats are in accordance with the requirements, in particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numerical data in CSV format such as raw measurement data of environmental variables. • Numerical data in Microsoft Excel® files formats such as processed measurement data. • Text description data in PDF files or in Markdown format such as reports and notes; occasionally these might be in Microsoft Word® or PowerPoint® files formats. • Images in common formats (e.g. JPG, TIFF, SVG) such as photographs of experiments. • Data from models may have formats such as Matlab® and R®. <p>Digital files produced by imaging detectors such as satellite data and the resulting soil moisture maps.</p>
<p>3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?</p>	<p><i>Purpose of the data generation or re-use</i></p> <p>The data generated and re-used originated from questionnaires, measurements, calibrations, models, comparisons and validations. They were used in meeting the project's objectives and in conferences and peer-reviewed publications. All technical WPs needed data generation and/or re-use to reach the targets stated in the deliverables.</p> <p><i>Data generated in relation to the objectives of the project</i></p> <p>Data were generated by the consortium in order to meet objectives 1 – 4. Measurement, commissioning, calibration and validation data result from objectives 1 and 2 and comparison and validation data from objectives 3 and 4. Data from questionnaires and stakeholder surveys were used by the consortium to decide what is relevant to the investigations done in this project and to support end-user uptake (objective 5).</p> <p>The project has generated and published the following datasets. In addition, other datasets are still being used for forthcoming publications and therefore cannot be made publicly available at the moment.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spreadsheets for soil samples and CRNS data processing, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7156607 2. Data in support to the manuscript Gianessi et al.,

	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7261534</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Data in support to the manuscript Grosse et al., https://doi.org/10.23728/b2share.db88e149f7924919be376909856739f1 4. Data in support to the manuscript Mazzoleni et al., https://zenodo.org/records/17177047 5. Data from interlaboratory comparison on soil moisture, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17723354 6. Data used to validate DTI transfer standard, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17283993 <p>Datasets 1 to 3 contribute to meeting objective 2. Dataset 4 contributes to meeting objective 3. Datasets 5 and 6 contribute to meeting objective 1.</p> <p><i>Data re-used in relation to the objectives of the project</i> The project re-used internal pre-existing data from the participants as well as publicly available data such as peer-reviewed articles found in scientific literature. Measurement, calibration, comparison and validation data were re-used by the consortium to meet objectives 1 – 4.</p>
<p>4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?</p>	<p>The overall size of the generated data was approximately 500 GB.</p>
<p>5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?</p>	<p><i>Data generated in the project</i> The data generated are from questionnaires, measurements, calibrations, models (numerical simulations), comparisons and validations.</p> <p>The provenance and context of the data were documented to meet relevant standards using the Provenance and Context Content Standard (PCCS) Matrix. The data are accompanied by information on how they were captured, processed and analysed. Other relevant information was also provided.</p> <p><i>Re-used data</i> The existing data originated from several sources, which included: participant's pre-existing data, data from the scientific literature, real-world measurement data and data from simulation experiments.</p>
<p>6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?</p>	<p>The data generated during the project realization are suitable for use by other research groups on the following topics: soil moisture monitoring, soil moisture sensors, calibration of soil moisture sensors, characterization of neutron detectors, precision farming, hydrological monitoring and forecasting, soil moisture harmonisation, data assimilation.</p> <p>The data generated by the project so far (cf. Q1) were made openly available and they are useful to the following communities: developers and users of the CRNS sensors, other scientists working in the field of applications of CRNS method to (agro)meteorology, hydrology, weather monitoring.</p> <p>It will also be useful for standards committees including CEN/TC 444/WG5 Environmental characterization/Physical tests, ISO/TC 190/WG1 and ISO/TC 190/SC3 Soil quality/Soil and Climate Change and Chemical and physical characterisation, WMO SC-MINT Standing Committee on Measurements, Instrumentation and Traceability, WMO INFCOM Commission for Observation,</p>

	<p>Infrastructure and Information Systems, EURAMET TC-T Technical Committee for Thermometry.</p> <p>The data might be useful to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders from industry: manufacturers of measurement instruments for soil moisture and other environmental variables, manufacturers of laboratory equipment for instrument calibration, developers of soil moisture monitoring systems and precision farming solutions. • Standardisation bodies: standards committees, see above. • NMIs/DIs that are planning to establish Calibration and Measurement Capabilities for moisture measurement and SI-traceable measurements of soil moisture on primary level. • Other scientists working in the fields: hydrological remote sensing, modelling and data assimilation, soil science, weather monitoring and forecasting. • Economic actors: companies operating in the fields of hydro-meteorological warnings, water resources management, flood control, agriculture and hydro-power plants. <p>Decision makers in water-related sectors such as irrigation management and planning, flood forecasting, early warnings.</p>
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1.2 Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) Data

1.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Questions	Answers
7 Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?	Yes, each of the project's deposited datasets is identified by the Digital Object Identifier (DOI).
8 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.	The metadata created for all of the project's deposited datasets was open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); the European Partnership on Metrology funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata will include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.
9 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?	Yes, discipline-specific search keywords were provided in the metadata to optimise the discovery and potential re-use of the deposited datasets, such as calibration, traceability, soil moisture monitoring, soil moisture harmonisation, CRNS (cosmic-ray neutron sensing), remote sensing soil moisture product, etc.
10 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Yes. The project's datasets and associated metadata were deposited in repositories such as Zenodo and B2SHARE EUDAT, ensuring the FAIRness (https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles) of data publishing.

1.2.2 Making data accessible

Questions	Answers
Repository:	

Questions	Answers
11 Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	<p>The project has deposited six datasets so far in trusted repositories. In addition, other datasets are still being used for forthcoming publications and therefore cannot be made publicly available at the moment.</p> <p>The data were made accessible by deposition in an open access repository. The project's 6 datasets and associated metadata were deposited in Zenodo (https://zenodo.org) and EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure (https://b2share.eudat.eu), respectively.</p>
12 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	No, the data were uploaded via a standard procedure and required no special arrangements.
13 Does the repository ensure that the data are assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	Yes, Zenodo and EUDAT assigned the DOI identifier to each of the project's deposited datasets.
Data:	
14 Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.	<p>All of the data that were needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications were made openly available (in trusted repositories such as Zenodo) as the default. There were reasons not to publish the data that was not included in the publications (see specific reasons below).</p> <p><i>Datasets which could not be shared – voluntary restrictions</i> Other data were not made available on a case-by-case basis as it was not relevant for third parties.</p> <p>The following data were not made publicly available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data obtained with the permission of third parties, but the third parties have not agreed to make the data public available. • Data disclosing the identity of a manufacturer. • Data compromising the protection of a participant(s) intellectual property. <p>The level of data made available was also considered. Pre-processed data were not provided as there was no clear reason for doing so.</p> <p><i>Datasets which could not be shared – legal and contractual reasons</i> The market survey data, which are commercially sensitive, could not be shared. Data not in compliance with the GDPR regulations were not made available.</p>
15 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.	<p>The data used in scientific publications, posters and oral communications were made available for re-use as soon as was reasonably possible. It is expected that the final data will be available for re-use after the end of the project. The first data used during project in scientific publications, posters and oral presentations will be made available for re-use earlier.</p> <p>The possibility of applying an embargo on some of the datasets will be decided by the Project Management Board on case-by-case basis. Should such a case arise, the embargo period will be discussed, set, and documented.</p> <p>The project has deposited 5 datasets in Zenodo and one dataset in EUDAT (see above). The following groups of datasets are expected to</p>

Questions	Answers
	<p>be deposited in trusted repositories such a Zenodo alongside the publication processes of related peer-reviewed publications:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Results from the neutron metrology laboratories 2. Results from the laboratories dealing with metrology of temperature and humidity 3. Datasets resulting from comparison measurement campaigns carried out on the project's outdoor test field sites
<p>16 Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</p>	<p>Yes, in case of Zenodo, well described conditions for free and standardised access are provided (http://about.zenodo.org/policies).</p>
<p>17 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</p>	<p>There are no restrictions on the use of the published data, but users will be required to acknowledge the European Partnership on Metrology program, the project, the consortium and the source of the data in any resulting publications and in any public use of the data (e.g., in presentations).</p>
<p>18 How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</p>	<p>There is no need to ascertain the identity of persons accessing the data.</p>
<p>19 Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</p>	<p>This consortium did not establish a Data Access Committee, because the project is not producing sensitive data. All results will be publicly available without restrictions, with the exception of data specified in Question 14.</p>
<p>Metadata:</p>	
<p>20 Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</p>	<p>The metadata created for all of the project's datasets will fulfil the repository's requirement for a minimum set of metadata.</p> <p>In case of Zenodo, metadata are licensed under CC0, except for email addresses. All metadata are exported via OAI-PMH and can be harvested. The metadata will contain information to enable the user to access the data.</p>
<p>21 How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data are no longer available?</p>	<p>The data will remain available, findable and reusable for the lifetime of the repositories used (see Question 11), which is expected to be at least 10 years.</p> <p>If data are withdrawn from the repository (e.g. Zenodo), the DOI and the URL of the original object are retained. In case of closure of the given repository, best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.</p>
<p>22 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data and will this be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?</p>	<p>Data can be read:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. By using openly available formats (ODT, PDF, MS Office, JPEG). 2. By sharing software to read the data. 3. By using specialised software: Matlab and Mathematica, Origin. <p>Standard publicly available software was used where possible. The majority of the software programmes are available as commercial products or as freeware.</p> <p>The project's 6 datasets which have been deposited in Zenodo and EUDAT i) are accessible using the following software tools, ii) require the</p>

Questions	Answers
	<p>following documentation about the software, and iii) require the following software:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spreadsheets for soil samples and CRNS data processing <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i) MS Office. ii) No specialist software is required. iii) No source codes required. 2. Data in support to the manuscript Gianessi et al. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i) MS Office, or other freely available software able to read data in csv format. ii) No specialist software is required. iii) No source codes required. 3. Data associated with the manuscript Grosse et al. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i) The comprehensive dataset comprises 16 individual subsets from different measurement methods. Part of the dataset (LiDAR imagery observations) is available in LAS file format. In addition, MS Office or other freely available software capable of reading CSV and TXT formats is required. ii) For the LiDAR LAS files, specialist software is required. iii) No source codes required. 4. Data associated with the manuscript Mazzoleni et al. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i) MS Office. ii) No specialist software is required. iii) No source codes required. 5. Data from interlaboratory comparison on soil moisture <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i) MS Office. ii) No specialist software is required. iii) No source codes required. 6. Data used to validate DTI transfer standard <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i) MS Office. ii) No specialist software is required. iii) No source codes required.

1.2.3 Making data interoperable

Questions	Answers
<p>23 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</p>	<p>The project's datasets and associated metadata use the trusted repository's basic metadata schema for administrative data, which is compliant with the recommended standards used by DataCite (https://search.datacite.org), OpenAIRE (https://www.openaire.eu) and BASE search (https://www.base-search.net).</p> <p>To guarantee the interoperability of project's data/research outputs, individual datasets are described using affirmed discipline-specific vocabularies, standards, formats, and methodologies, including but not limited e.g., GUM, OBO foundry, DICOM, NetCDF, HDF5, CityGML, INSPEC, ISO 9001.</p>
<p>24 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to</p>	<p>No mappings are necessary, as the datasets are described using standard terminologies.</p>

allow their re-use, refinement or extension?	
25 Will your data include qualified references ¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	Yes, the project's datasets deposited in the chosen repository (e.g. Zenodo) included qualified references to other datasets from the same project and/or to other datasets from previous research.

1.2.4 Increase data re-use

Questions	Answers
26 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?	A short README file (e.g. in Markdown format) was provided together with the data, in order to enable data analysis and to facilitate data re-use.
27 Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?	<p>The data were licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) version 4.0. Users will be required to acknowledge the European Partnership on Metrology program, the project, the consortium and the source of the data in any resulting publications.</p> <p>The project's 6 datasets which have been deposited in Zenodo and EUDAT, respectively, include the following licenses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spreadsheets for soil samples and CRNS data processing Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International 2. Data in support to the manuscript Gianessi et al. Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International 3. Data in support to the manuscript Grosse et al. Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International 4. Data in support to the manuscript Mazzoleni et al. Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International 5. Data from interlaboratory comparison on soil moisture Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International 6. Data used to validate DTI transfer standard Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
28 Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<p>The data published in open-access journals are usable by third parties as the datasets have been deposited in Zenodo and EUDAT. The data that do not relate to peer-reviewed publications were not made available.</p> <p>Up to now there are no restrictions foreseen for the datasets that have been and/or will be deposited by the project. It is expected that all</p>

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

Questions	Answers
	datasets produced and deposited by the project will be useable also after the end of the project.
29 Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Yes, the provenance and context of the data was thoroughly documented to meet relevant standards using the Provenance and Context Content Standard (PCCS) Matrix (cf. https://eos.org/opinions/the-importance-of-data-set-provenance-for-science). Data were accompanied by information on how they were captured, processed, analysed, and validated. Other information that enables interpretation was also provided.
30 Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.	Each participant is assuring the data quality by working according to each internal certified quality management system and certified technical procedures. Generally, data quality is assured through repeated measurements, adherence to standards for data recording, the use of controlled vocabularies and standard terminology, through the metrological characterisation of the measurement set-ups, provision of test results along with the data and through the validation of the data collected.
31 Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.	<i>Allocation of resources</i> The estimated costs for making the (data and) other research outputs FAIR were 3,000 € (personnel costs), see Question 34. The costs for making other research outputs FAIR were included in the project's budget and will be claimed if compliant with the Grant Agreement's conditions. The Project Management Board (PMB) had also overall responsibility for managing other research outputs (see Question 36). Where feasible, long-term preservation was ensured by depositing the other research outputs in repositories. The PMB decided on a case-by-case basis on which other research outputs were deposited and for how long. <i>Security of other research outputs</i> The participants stored other research outputs on their organisations' networks, which are protected by firewall, backups etc. Other research outputs were also stored in the project's SharePoint environment, with password-protected login. Deposition in public repositories provides additional security as they have multiple replicas in a distributed file system which is backed up on a nightly basis. This project did not generate sensitive other research outputs. The other research outputs are safely stored in open access repositories. <i>Ethical aspects</i> Ethical issues are discussed by the PMB on case-by-case basis and addressed as the project prepared an ethics report. The project did not share other research outputs with identifiable personal information. Sensitive information relating to the other research outputs were collected, separated as soon as possible, and kept secure.

1.3 Other research outputs

Questions	Answers
32 In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated	The new calibration methods and protocols produced by the project will be published in form of peer-reviewed scientific publications, project deliverables and reports. The most suitable form of publication will be decided by the Project Management Board on case-by-case basis. The project has created and maintains a project-specific community on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/sommet . In addition to peer-

Questions	Answers
or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).	reviewed scientific publications, the Zenodo community page will host further project reports, presentations (e.g. from the project training course) and similar outputs.
33 Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.	As far as possible, the FAIR data approaches specified in Questions 7 – 30 above will be applied to the management of this project's other research outputs. This commitment will be met by releasing the new software that will be developed in the project under license, by placing the new calibration methods, and protocols, in a repository and by patenting the new materials that will be developed in the project in line with the requirements of the project's consortium agreement.

1.4 Allocation of resources

Questions	Answers
34 What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?	The estimated costs for making the data and other research outputs Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) were 3,000 € (personnel costs). The costs were kept to a minimum by using a free trusted repository (see Question 11) and by making only relevant data and other outputs FAIR.
35 How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the European partnership on metrology grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).	The costs for making the data FAIR were included in the project's budget and will be claimed if compliant with the Grant Agreement's conditions.
36 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?	Each participant assures sound data quality (see Question 30) as well as appropriate research data archiving. The initial responsibility for the proper data management of a given dataset (or record, software, etc.) lies with the partner who created the dataset. Furthermore, the following project participants have been appointed as data coordinators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PTB as project coordinator and WP6 produced data WP leaders: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DTI for WP1 produced data - UP DE for WP2 produced data - UNIBO for WP3 produced data - CNR for WP4 produced data - INRIM for WP5 produced data - PTB as project webpage host administrator PTB as project webpage content administrator
37 How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who	Long-term preservation was ensured by depositing the data within trusted repositories. There were no costs associated with the long-term preservation of the data in these repositories. The potential value of the data will likely increase over time because of its fundamental impact in a wide range of applications (there is the

decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?	possibility that some data may become superseded by more up-to-date data). The data will also be of value as it underpins the results of published datasets. The Project Management Board decides on a case-by-case basis on what data will be kept and for how long.
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1.5 Data security

Questions	Answers
38 What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	<i>Data recovery and secure storage</i> All participants store data on their organisations' networks, which are protected by firewall, backups, etc. Data are also stored in the project's SharePoint environment, with password protected login. Deposition in the Zenodo public repository provided additional security as it has multiple replicas in a distributed file system which is backed up on a nightly basis. <i>Transfer of sensitive data</i> This project did not generate sensitive data.
39 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?	Yes, the data are safely stored in open access repository, see Question 11. The repositories are certified for long-term data preservation and curation.

1.6 Ethics

Questions	Answers
40 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics report(s) and the ethics section in the Annex 1.	It is not expected that there will be any ethical or legal issues that will affect the project data sharing. All data coming from third parties, e.g. manufacturers, will be shared only after obtaining explicit consent by the owners. Data from the market surveys/questionnaires will be made anonymous to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
41 Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	The project did not share data with identifiable personal information and it is not planning to do so. If any sensitive data will be collected, they will be separated and kept secure.

1.7 Other issues

Questions	Answers
42 Do you, or will you, make use of other national / funder / sectorial / departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?	Data management was compliant with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The research data policy of the European Partnership on Metrology; • European laws about data security and the protection of privacy (e.g. GDPR); • Institutional guidelines; Scientific community guidelines.

2 Open science: research data management

Statement	Put an X in the box to confirm	Or, list any exceptions to this
All participants have adhered to the requirements of the project's GA and CA with respect to open science: research data management (GA Article 17 and its Annex 5) for this reporting period	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	